

Empowering Voices: The Role of Civil Society in Human Rights Advocacy and International Accountability

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Abstract

The CSOs are obviously NGOs and grass-root movements holding a strategic place in global protection and promotion of human rights. This paper analyses their functions in advocate human rights, especially oppressive regimes or war-torn areas. NGOs utilize various strategies ranging legal advocacy, reporting, monitoring, public campaigns, to associations with international bodies. Their efforts are in fact most important in holding governments accountable domestically and internationally. The paper looks at the legal basis that enables functions carried out by civil society through instruments such as the ICCPR¹ and the UN Declaration on Human Rights Defenders, among others, and through mechanisms such as the ICC and the UPR. Repressive contexts present obstacles to CSOs along categorized lines but include oppressive laws, harassment, and physical intimidation. The paper will rely on the legal aspect, case laws, and empirical evidence to demonstrate that civil society plays an important role in maintaining a great degree of human rights internationally. Case studies on several topics like restrictive NGO laws in Egypt, the Rohingya crisis in Myanmar, and the Jasmine Revolution of Tunisia will be drawn upon to outline how grassroots movements and NGOs can influence accountability and human rights protection.

1. Introduction

Civil society has been at the forefront in shaping the global human rights context. Mega agglomeration of actors from non-governmental organizations includes the grassroots movements, CBOs, religious institutions, and advocacy groups form civil society which works outside the lines of government structures but seeks to represent the interests of thousands and thousands of people and communities who are subjected to disadvantage and oppression. In the language of human rights, civil society is both advocate and watchdog, holding governments and international institutions to account for the fulfilment of human rights commitments. The paper traces the ways NGOs² and grassroots movements, among others within civil society, contribute

¹https://www.ohchr.org/en/ohchr_homepage?gad_source=1&gclid=Cj0KCQjwsc24BhDPArisAFXqAB05_EdRNeXAD9QtsX5F7xzIaxvOpQm1Tn-szfHD6pCJyXHm8r9Ms-waAmzWEALw_wcB

² Adair, A., 1999, "Code of Conduct for NGOs — A Necessary Reform", Institute of Economic Affairs.

to protection and promotion of human rights, principally in countries where the struggle against oppressive regimes or civil war has made this work both urgent and dangerous.³

Human rights violations take place in almost all regions involved all over the globe, particularly in countries ruled by an authoritarian regime or under armed conflict. Civil society actors have often been the last resort to fighting against both states and non-states accused of such violations. Civil society organizations report violations both through advocacy and through litigation, monitor the incidence of such activities, and engage in public campaigns to affect legal and systemic change. Their impact is thus significant beyond national borders because civil society organizations, more broadly, are transnational, mobilizing international attention and leveraging international mechanisms of accountability. This role endows civil society with an integral place within the global regime of human rights.⁴

1.1 What is Civil Society in the Human Rights Context?

The sum total of independent organizations and institutions of civil society reflects the interests and values of individuals and communities, independent of those of the state or private sector. Civil society is important to have an untainted say from those in government processes to have a voice. In the context of human rights, civil society actors range from large, international NGOs like Amnesty International and Human Rights Watch, to smaller, locally based grassroots organizations located in affected communities.⁵

Civil society organizations typically tend to work between the state and the market so that they do not respond to the pressures and incentives of either. This independence gives an important reason that makes civil society very central in the process of the human rights advocacy-it provides a counter to the state power, challenge violations, and call for accountability. Most importantly, civil society has an educative function, enlightening citizens on their rights and how to claim protection thereof.

1.2 The Global Legal Framework Supporting Civil Society

Civil society actors rely on both national and international instruments of law for the achievement of their activities, protection against retaliation, and notification of violators of their rights. Such international instruments as the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and the United Nation's Declaration on Human Rights Defenders have become important guarantees for the actors. For instance, it grants them basic rights like the right to expression, the right to assemble, and the right to associate-all of which are precursors for civil society actors to

³<https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/document?repid=rep1&type=pdf&doi=4d8d4d0575416628d5862e0f6b61b17e7de6e6d7>

⁴ Eigen, Peter, "The Central Role of Civil Society in Combating Corruption in the Era of Globalization", paper presented at Transparency for Growth Conference, Atlanta, Georgia, 1999.

⁵ Human Development Report, 1993, United Nations Development Program, United Nations

have activities conducted in an interference-free environment. Article 22 specifically protects the right to freedom of association as a core component of civil society activity.⁶

The other international instrument is the UN Declaration on Human Rights Defenders adopted in 1998, which upholds the legitimate role of civil society as played in the defence of human rights. It declared that persons and groups have the right to promote and protect human rights and called upon states to respect and ensure protection for human rights defenders from violence, threats, retaliation, and other forms of intimidation. Even though it has no legally binding force, this declaration constitutes a kind of normative framework that civil society actors could claim or raise protests against limitations or violations committed by authorities.

National levels, civil society is also immersed in domestic legal frameworks that may either be supportive or restrictive of its activities. Generally, in democratic states, constitutional guarantees and specific legislation ascertain the freedom of assembly and expression, which protected civil society. In authoritarian regimes, however, there are often laws that prevent civil society from fulfilling its functions. In most cases, the undesirable legal framework may take the form of a taxing registration process, foreign funding prohibitions, or penal laws imposed on the leaders of civil society organizations. Taking this into account, civil society actors in repressive states are operating in a Gray zone, where, in some cases, law was defined to limit their ability.⁷

1.3 Civil Society in Repressive and Conflict-Affected Environments

Organizations in civil society often suffer from severe constraints in authoritarian regimes and war zones. For governments that are intent on consolidating their power or suppressing dissension, civil society may be considered a challenge to national security or stability. It is possible for such governments to apply strait-jacket legal instruments, to organize intimidation campaigns, or even to resort to direct violence against activists and organizations. Under such circumstances, there is always a possibility to operate civil society; creative strategies allow activists to circumvent state repression.

In repressive contexts, NGOs and grassroots movements often rely on digital tools and international networks to keep their activities alive. The online environment gives such groups the means to issue calls to action, mobilize campaigns, and coordinate with allies elsewhere. These have been particularly useful to countries whose more conventional organizing forms, such as public demonstrations or meetings, are monitored and banned.⁸

International support is what cushions civil society actors to carry on with activities in hostile environments. Such international NGOs as the UN and the European Union, among many others, provide funding and mechanisms for capacity building and protection of civil society organizations at risk. International agencies open up the opportunity to submit reports on

⁶ file:///C:/Users/ASNA%20JABI/Downloads/Civil_Society_Organizations_and_Service_Provision.pdf

⁷ <https://www.proquest.com/openview/c88a36f6c56b30b77cd33bf974851277/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=2823>

⁸ Ahrne, Goran (1994) *The Organizing of Individuals and Society: Interaction Inside, Outside and Between Organizations*. London: Sage.

violations of human rights and act as bridges between local civil society and global accountability structures.⁹

1.4 Civil Society and Advocacy and Accountability:

Organizations of civil society have played a crucial role in articulating both the national and international policies regarding human rights. Advocacy has formed a major basis for pushing legal reforms and strengthening human rights protections. Most importantly, civil society organizations have been known to check government power through bringing state actors accountable before the citizenry for his or her violations of human rights. In many instances, civil society organizations are the ones unearthing the violations and bringing proof thereof to the international bodies- namely, the UN Human Rights Council, the International Criminal Court (ICC), or regional human rights courts.¹⁰

The advocacy process is another role civil society plays in ensuring accountability for past violations, especially in post-conflict situations. In many cases, the process of documenting violations, representing victims, and claiming justice is initiated and undertaken by civil society organizations. South Africa, Chile, and Colombia are good examples where civil society has played a huge role in advocating for justice and reconciliation following state-led violence and repression.

Civil society serves as a very powerful catalyst for accountability, justice, and the rule of law within adversarial regimes and conflict areas where government and individual accountability is perceived to be lacking. Because human rights abuse cannot be hidden even in the most oppressive of conditions, civil society represents an indispensable element of the global human rights movement.

Civil society organizations play an extremely important role in pushing for human rights promotion. Civil society firms function amidst often hostile environments, but through their organizing work, civil society firms remain a cornerstone of human rights advocacy, accountability to state power, amplifying the unheard voice, and working with righteous zeal to fulfil these norms domestically and internationally. In this paper, further clarity is brought to the specifics on how civil society promotes human rights and what challenges they face in repressive and conflicted environments and the frameworks of law that allow them to function effectively towards the advancement of human rights.

Advocacy Practices of Civil Society

⁹ <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/135050849631006>

¹⁰ Keeley, Michael (1988) *A Social-Contract Theory of Organizations*. Notre Dame, IN: University of Notre Dame Press.

Civil society organizations implement several advocacy strategies to advocate and promote human rights in different parts of the globe. These advocacy strategies take a stand in formulating legal actions, public campaigns, awareness-building initiatives, cooperative relations with international organizations, and comprehensive documentation and reporting of abuses. This brings together all the others for CSOs to take an important role in advocating accountability and justice, primarily in regimes of oppressors and conflict-affected regions where the other state institutions fail to fulfil their role to protect human rights.¹¹

2.1 Advocacy through Law

Perhaps one of the best tools available to civil society organizations is legal advocacy, through which nongovernmental organizations and grassroots movements can strategically litigate against unjust laws or practices at both the domestic and international level. Legal advocacy could thus be symbolic, for example when filing *amicus curiae* briefs or direct lawsuits brought before courts as well as where litigation support is afforded victims against perpetrators such as governments or other non-state actors who violate their human rights.

- **Domestic Legal Advocacy:** Advocates, especially in most countries, take cases of marginalized people who would otherwise not have the capacity to challenge violations backed by the state. For example, in India, NGOs litigate police brutality, minority rights, and gender-based violence to just name a few.

International Advocacy NGOs also play an important role in international law advocacy, which may include filing cases before international bodies including the European Court of Human Rights (ECHR), the Inter-American Court of Human Rights (IACHR), and the African Court on Human and Peoples' Rights¹². In *Loizidou v. Turkey*, a Turkish Cypriot woman assisted by NGOs presented her petition before the ECHR when Turkey occupied Northern Cyprus; she was compensated for damages on the violation of the right to property. The case not only brought comfort to the petitioner but also became a legal jurisprudence for future cases on human rights.¹³ International treaty-making advocates formulation, ratification, and implementation of international human rights instruments in the CSOs. In this regard, a great deal of the NGO's role lies in lobbying to adopt the Rome Statute that birthed the ICC as well as the haste in the ratification of the CRPD.

2.2 Public Campaigns and Awareness-Raising

Public advocacy and awareness creation will always be central work of CSOs in advocating causes of human rights. These advocacy efforts seek to raise awareness, mobilize public support for, and put pressure on governments or international bodies into action regarding allegedly

¹¹ <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/books/mono/10.4324/9781849770736/civil-society-helmut-anheier>

¹² <https://www.cambridge.org/core/books/abs/constitutional-courts-in-asia/towards-more-intraasian-judicial-cooperation-in-the-constitutional-sphere/CFECE5907F62476BB0DE1F6395E19B80>

¹³ <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/1464988032000051469>

committed human rights violations. Speed and wide reach in cyberspace have maximized information and organizing possibilities in public advocacy.¹⁴

- **Campaigns on Specific Human Rights Issues:** Most NGOs implement campaigns on certain rights or abuses. For example, Amnesty International has a campaign called "Write for Rights," mobilizing millions of people across the world to pen and send letters and messages to the government requesting them to free political prisoners or to put an end to torture. Campaigns are raised to heighten public awareness on the specific cases brought about by such abuses and pressure governments to reform the given policies.
- **Mass Mobilizations:** Grassroots movements usually use street protests and demonstrations to change society. The "**Black Lives Matter**" movement represents a case where local protests and reformation of grassroots movements against police brutality shaped a global movement demanding racial justice and police reforms.

2.3 Human Rights Violation Monitoring and Record

Advocacy involves systematic monitoring and reporting of human rights violations cases. Most international organizations dealing with human rights use this approach in an effort to accumulate more evidence about violations based on fact-finding missions. Such evidence leads to reports, by which governments are held liable. Organizations such as HRW and Amnesty International research and undertake fact-finding missions on evidence of violation and write reports to call governments to account. These reports usually find their way into such international organizations as the **United Nations Human Rights Council (UNHRC)** and regional human rights bodies; from there, the reports are used to influence decision-making over, and policy reforms for, the concerned areas.¹⁵

- **Documentations of Violations:** Human rights actors often investigate, document abuses, and publish in detail reports of evidence in cases of human rights violation. During the armed conflict that crippled Syria, for example, various organizations documented war crimes that were committed during this conflict, which were critical for international organizations and courts.¹⁶
- **Public Reporting:** In authoritarian countries where free press is banned, NGOs stand as alternate credible reporting agencies. They report atrocities of authoritarian regimes in their country as well as outside.

2.4 International Partnerships and Advocacy

It is convenient for civil society organizations to coordinate more readily with international organizations and institutions to make their advocacies more accessible and louder. For example,

¹⁴ Paul, J.A., 2000, "NGOs and Global Policy-Making", Global Policy Forum.

¹⁵ <https://content.iospress.com/articles/statistical-journal-of-the-united-nations-economic-commission-for-europe/sju00487>

¹⁶ <https://academic.oup.com/ejil/article/23/4/1089/546164>

it cooperates with bodies such as the UN, the EU, and many regional human rights courts to make CSOs voice themselves better in the international arena.

- **International Mechanisms:** Civil Society Organizations play an active role in international human rights mechanisms, especially the UNHRC's Universal Periodic Review, UPR. The UPR allows NGOs to submit shadow reports of issues of human rights matters not necessarily reported by a state and make and provide a more balanced and comprehensive review of a country's human rights record.¹⁷

2.5 Grass roots lobbying and community engagement

The grass roots level civil society actors work in communities to empower individuals, promote human rights from the bottom upwards, and build grass roots democracy, many working through local NGOs that engage directly with vulnerable populations to raise them up to their rights and train them in advocating for them. Grass roots organizations then play a key mediator role between warring parties in most of the conflict zones by proposing solutions that put the protection of civilians and their rights at the center.

- **Community-Based Human Rights Education:** Grass-root organizations in the illiterate or ignorant societies also educate the people directly about their rights. This grass-root ownership, therefore, gives credence to local human rights operations and makes human rights not only an abstract concept but a part of everyday life.

3. Civil Society and Mechanisms for Accountability

Civil society organizations at both national and international levels are very foundational to building and developing mechanisms for accountability. In the context of human rights, the term accountability is used to refer to the duty of governments and other actors not classified as state but performing state functions- to answer for their acts and, where such acts result in violations, to provide reparation to victims. Civil society serves as an institution that brings violators of human rights before the book through varied mechanisms of law, politics, and social pressures.

3.1 International Responsibility

Civil society has a very positive role at the international level since it ensures responsibility both on states' parts and other powerful actors. Non-governmental organizations usually interact with international human rights institutions such as the International Criminal Court, UN treaty bodies, and regional human rights courts.¹⁸

- **International Criminal Court (ICC):** The Rome Statute established the ICC, which, therefore has become a great landmark for international law, but provided a means to hold individuals responsible for war crimes, crimes against humanity, and genocide. Civil society organizations have been active in campaigns associated with the formation of the

¹⁷ Human Development Report, 2003, "Millennium Development Goal: A Compact Among Nations to End Human Poverty", United Nations Development Programme.

¹⁸ <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/13642987.2018.1492916>

ICC and remain an effective advocate for information and evidence submission to create prosecution opportunities. For instance, in the continuing investigations about the atrocities against people of the Democratic Republic of Congo, documentary evidence and mainly witness testimony have been particularly significant for civil societies.¹⁹

- **Universal Periodic Review (UPR):** NGOs always do shadow reports in the process of UPR, an alternative assessment of the country's performance regarding human rights. Often such reports bring to light issues omitted by or covered up by the government; hence, it is rather more complete and more accurate.²⁰

3.2 Domestic Accountability

At the national level, civil society organizations often engage with governmental accountability efforts at the legislative or litigation levels, advocate for policy reforms, or seek to expose corruption and abuses of power. An important watchdog function by civil society is seen when rule-of-law approaches are weak; attention to the activities of government are always exercised and obligations placed on the government under international human rights law are kept up.²¹

- **Litigation for Accountability:** Domestic litigation is the most potent tool by which CSOs can sustain their call for accountability. This has been the case, powerfully in post-apartheid South Africa, where civil society efforts have laid ground for the creation of the Truth and Reconciliation Commission as a measure of redressing past human rights violations. CSOs have become vital for ensuring the government makes transitions to reform, paving the way for legislative actions to be carried out on behalf of the most marginalized groups.

3.3 Civil Society in Transitional Justice in Post-Conflict Situations

In transitional justice cases after a conflict, the role of civil society is very significant. Whichever processes of transitional justice have been involved in the post-conflict process will always depend on the input and influence of civil society. The documentation of atrocities, representation of victims, and campaigning for reparation as well as reform measures to prevent such maltreatment in the future depends on the help of CSOs.

- **Truth and Reconciliation Commissions:** Civil society actors have been strong advocates for the creation of truth commissions in most countries moving out of conflict or authoritarian rule, whose task has been to establish facts about human rights violations under those regimes and to propose remedies. The South African TRC, so widely endorsed by CSOs, has been a model from which other countries could draw in establishing mechanisms for dealing with past abuses.

¹⁹ <https://library.oapen.org/handle/20.500.12657/24095>

²⁰ <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/chapters/edit/10.4324/9780203862179-15/international-criminal-court-william-schabas>

²¹ Mendelson, Why Governments Target Civil Society, 2

3.4 Barriers to Accountability

The most daunting challenges faced by civil society organizations in ensuring accountability are the repressive climate which, sometimes, heralds that government is not willing to cooperate and may even be an enemy to justice, while around the world, civil society actors are hounded, legally constrained, and put under violence for their efforts in the pursuit of justice and accountability. As often as not, the governments of the land enact stringent laws that further curtail their capacity to operate or accept foreign funding, thereby weakening their capacity to make violators accountable.

4. Inhibitive Challenges

Civil Society Organizations Face in Conflict Zones and Repressive Nations The civil society is today exposed to numerous risks and challenges as it goes about its activities in zones of conflict and repressive states. More than other environs, these places impose strict limitations on rights of freedom of speech, association, and assembly; they expose human rights defenders to higher risks of violence, harassment, and prosecution.²²

4.1 Legal and Regulatory Barriers

Many governments establish legal systems imposed to sustain the operations of civil society organizations but at the same time groomed with some authoritarianism. These laws entail strict registration procedures and deprivation of NGOs' freedom to receive foreign funding, as well as criminal activities in the name of national security or public order against human rights defenders.

- **Restrictive NGO laws:** Several laws passed in Egypt have restricted the practice of NGOs. The 2019 NGO law requires a no objection certificate from the government for the running of activities, does not allow them to engage with political work and sharply limits foreign sources of funding. These legal barriers severely limit the scale at which the civil society sector might function effectively to request a change in policy.²³

4.2 Harassment and Intimidation

There can be states as well as non-states who usually harass and intimidate civil society organizations as well as human rights defenders. Impacts can be given in bodily injury, arrest, imprisonment, even extrajudicial killing. Targeting civil society leaders has been a usual situation among the common means to suppress dissent and crack on promoting human rights in repressive environments.

- **Targeted Violence Against Activists:** There are intimidations of activists in such countries as Russia and Venezuela that are arbitrarily detained or expelled. At times, human rights defenders are even murdered because of their activities, just like in the case

²² Venice Commission, Hungary: Draft Law on the Transparency, 12.

²³ Melucci, Alberto (1988) 'Social Movements and the Democratization of Everyday Life', in John Keane (ed.) Civil Society and the State: New European Perspectives. London: Verso.

of Honduran environmental and indigenous rights defender Berta Cáceres, murdered for her opposition to illegal land projects.

4.3 Digital Surveillance and Censorship

More and more, governments of oppressive regimes make use of the digital world to monitor and suppress civil society activities. The state resorts to modern instruments of surveillance using the most advanced technological tools to monitor activists' communication, hack into NGO data banks, and censor net content. It makes civil society work much more complicated, particularly for those working in countries that have developed huge state surveillance systems.

- **Internet censorship and control:** China's government has set an environment strictly controlled and impotent for the civil society organizations freely to express information and organize campaigns. International NGOs can hardly access Chinese audiences due to the "Great Firewall," yet local organizations are constantly being censored and monitored.

4.4 Physical and Psychological Risks

In areas covered by outbreaks of armed conflicts, physical and psychological risk is heightened for civil society actors who carry on operations. Human rights defenders may get caught up in crossfire in areas where open armed conflicts are taking place or kidnapped or killed. Gross violations of human rights and constant threats may become unbearable for activists and members of the staff of civil society organizations.

- **Humanitarian workers and human rights defenders:** They have lost and suffered much. Actors in civil society tasked with humanitarian work, as well as documenting war crimes, have fallen victims of targeted attacks, among them in Syria, Yemen, and other countries. Most targeted killings have been those of these actors, while others have been kidnapped and tormented by groups of armed men.²⁴

5. Civil Society Impact Case Studies

This chapter outlines case studies on how civil society organizations may be used as a leverage to promote human rights, call for accountability, and advance the cause of justice within repressive regimes and situations of conflict.

5.1 Tunisia: Civil Society and the Jasmine Revolution

An excellent case is the Jasmine Revolution of 2010-2011 in Tunisia, which exemplifies the central role civil society can play in underpinning political change. Actors involved in the protests against the regime of President Zine El Abidine Ben Ali were characterized by trade unions and human rights groups as well as by youth movements. Such activism finally led to

²⁴ Pateman, Carole (1988) 'The Fraternal Social Contract', in John Keane (ed.) Civil Society and the State: New European Perspectives. London: Verso.

overthrowing a long-time authoritarian leader and to forming a democratically elected government.

In Tunisia, the UGTT and LTDH mobilized citizens toward democratic reforms. The workers' union proved marvellous in leadership and organization and made sure that the revolution retained all its democratic and human rights framework for all the Tunisians.

5.2 Egypt: Challenges for NGOs under Oppressive Laws

That was very different in Tunisia, where civil society NGOs were not as oppressed after the Arab Spring uprising. Egyptian president Abdel Fattah el-Sisi has since passed laws controlling NGOs such that they no longer function independently. This notwithstanding, there are still human rights advocacy NGOs in Egypt aggressively pushing through their campaigns under constant threats of governmental retribution.

- **Human Rights NGOs:** Organizations like the Egyptian Initiative for Personal Rights (EIPR) have chronicled all manner of human rights abuses in Egypt- from torture and arbitrary detention to suppression of freedom of expression. And while the government does harass and imprison them, there is little shortage of critical voices outside Myanmar's shrinking civil society space.

5.3 Myanmar: Civil Society and the Rohingya Crisis

Actually, it is Myanmar civil society organizations that kept really significant records of the crisis faced by Rohingya and brought international attention toward them. It is the local NGOs as well as global NGOs which are collecting the evidences of those ethnic cleansing, mass killings, and sexual violation upon Rohingya Muslim population through Myanmar military.

- **Role of NGOs in Documentation and Advocacy:** Just like in Fortify Rights and Free Rohingya Coalition operating from Myanmar, organizations documented all human rights violation and fought for international intervention. For example through their efforts, several cases have been opened in the ICC and also on pressure caused to UN for more serious actions.

5.4 South Africa: Civil Society in Post-Apartheid Transitional Justice

Deep reflection is required in taking into consideration the position of civil society in South Africa as the country transitioned from the apartheid regime to democracy. Since the TRC's determination was based on finding out the extent of previous human rights abuses, a large group of civil society actors were seen to be providing support in having victims' voices told and their justice presented.²⁵

Civil society organizations, religious institutions, and NGOs became big advocates of the creation and continued life work towards justice and reconciliation. That is why it becomes a

²⁵ Tester, Keith (1992) Civil Society. London: Routledge.

model in any post-conflict society, showing the role, that civil society plays in transitional justice activities.²⁶

6.The Future of Civil Society in Human Rights Advocacy

The landscape of international politics will continue to change, both challenging and offering civil society scope to develop and protect the interests of human rights. Irrespective of such unavoidable evidence, further populist, nationalistic, and even authoritarian trends undeniably constrict the space available to civil society activity. The risk far outweighs the gain in advocacies of their current forms with technology advancement.

6.1 Advancement of Authoritarianism and Shrinking Civic Space

During the last decade, the global scenario, whether in Eastern Europe, Latin America, or Southeast Asia, has seen a trend of increasing authoritarianism and populism. Such political trends lead to the decreasing civic space as governments are passing laws to reduce civil society activities and create a threat to freedom of speech and assembly.

➤ **What are the effects on civil society?**

Authoritarian erosion of the sphere of civil liberties can be witnessed in the devastation of Hungary, Turkey, and Venezuela: civil society organizations are the first to lose from repression. Countries in which NGOs are viewed as agents of foreign powers or elements dangerous to the state subject them to extreme levels of control or completely forbid activities.²⁷

6.2 Online Advocacy: Challenges and Opportunities

Advocacy for human rights is facing a new generation in the form of new technology. This is the first time in history when there are more ways to engage civil society activism, fundraising, and cooperation across the globe using social media platforms, digital organizing tools, and blockchain technology. However, these technologies also pose grave challenges: the threats of digital surveillance, cyberattacks, and the spread of misinformation.

This digital advocacy opportunity has been brought about by the creation of social media, including Twitter, Facebook, and Instagram. Gross human rights abuses are exposed, and people start mobilizing for a given cause, such as what occurred with the #MeToo movement that started from social media-as a grassroots revolution that can be likened to any other social movement that has occurred worldwide advocating for gender equality and accountability for sexual harassment and assault.²⁸

➤ **Issues with Digital Surveillance:** States, whether authoritarian or democratic, have become owners of the application of technology methods of monitoring and regulating

²⁶ Ndegwa, S.N., 1996, "The Two Faces of Civil Society — NGOs and Politics in Africa", Kumarian Press, Inc.

²⁷ Touraine, Alain (1981) *The Voice and the Eye: An Analysis of Social Movements*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press

²⁸ Brunsson, Nils (1985) *The Irrational Organization: Irrationality as a Basis for Organizational Action and Change*. Chichester: Wiley.

civil society activities. Digital surveillance, hacking, and content censorship to which states resort in regard to online content normally limit the scope and influence of civil society organizations. This places NGOs between a rock and a hard place in so far as creating significant investments in their digital security to ensure communications and data are secure.

6.3 Globalization and Transnational Networks

This growing interconnectivity in the world facilitates civil society organizations' ability to build transnational networks—that is, border-spanning coalitions—that enable communicative coordination between organizations and collaboration over resources and strategies for urgent issues, assistance in strengthening the advocacy itself.

- **Transnational Advocacy Networks:** Such international federations for human rights and the like—including, say, the International Campaign to Ban Landmines—often exemplify how transnational networks can achieve such prominent victories for human rights. This includes the case of ICBL mobilizing tens of thousands of people toward a successful advocacy campaign leading to the Mine Ban Treaty signed in 1997 which banned the use, stockpiling, and production of anti-personnel landmines.²⁹

6.4 International Organizations and Donors

It becomes an inalienable complement to their enabling function for civil society, in general under repressive regimes and hot spots, where mobilization from domestic sources may be difficult. However, foreign funding dependency is a two-edged sword, since arguments most frequently used by governments to defame and delegitimize all civil society organisations are those on dependency.

- **International backup for Civil Society:** The UN, EU, and other international NGOs fill in the gap to provide the local human rights defenders and organizations with needed financial and technical input. Capacity-building programs, funding opportunities, and even international advocacy platforms are possible for civil society in continuing their work even in hostile environments.

6.5 Prospect for Human Rights Advocacy: Civil Society

Still, despite all these setbacks, it is still civil society organizations which will be the voice in protection and promotion of human rights. The more chaotic the stormy global political climate, the more civil society must adapt through new technologies, transnational alliances, and new advocacy strategies. It is how resilient civil society can be in facing repression that determines future directions for the global human rights movement.

²⁹ <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/15562948.2015.1017632>

Conclusion

Civil society is most important in the promotion and protection of human rights because it acts as an institution that bridges between the state and individual and holds governments and other players responsible for their actions. The states' power also fails somewhere, and NGOs, grassroots movements, or the most vulnerable and marginalized civil society organization is supposed to be filled. This conclusion unmasks those key ways in which civil society contributes to human rights advocacy, accountability, and justice, simultaneously holding together reflections on what such promotion of its role may mean in the face of globalization's changes.

1. The Multiple Facets of Civil Society Concerning Human Rights Advocacy

Civil society organizations have a whole range of related activities meant to promote human rights. They are challenging unjust laws using legal advocacy, pushing cases before both domestic and international courts, and ensuring accountability of governments toward their human rights obligations.³⁰

Public awareness and agitation regarding issues of human rights is the other very important role of civil society. This can be achieved through mobilization, mass demonstrations, and sensitization campaigns toward citizens that call for policy reforms. Digital platforms have very lately turned out to be important in public advocacy, through which civil society organizations can easily mobilize world support by compelling the governments as well as international organizations to take action for human rights protection and reform.

Civil society, therefore, in conflict situations and within oppressive regimes plays an equally important role in documenting and reporting human rights abuses. Organizations, for example, such as Amnesty International and Human Rights Watch have developed extensive research whose reports provide irreplaceable evidence in judicial cases before international courts and human rights mechanisms. In circumstances where there is suppression of free independent media or no free press at all, then this monitoring function becomes very important, and civil society will be a reliable source of credible information regarding the violations.³¹

Civil society has a role to play as well in transitional justice. Organizations pushing for post-conflict or post-authoritarian societies place great emphasis on the fact that justice mechanisms such as truth commissions, reparations programmes, and war crimes tribunals do full justice to the past abuses. Actors here portray and represent the victims by advocating for reparations with a view to ensuring that justice mechanisms are inclusive and transparent. In fact, South Africa's Truth and Reconciliation Commission supported by organizations of civil society stands out as the most exemplary vehicle of these actors towards healing and justice for divided societies.

2. Accountability: A Central Pillar of Civil Society's Work

³⁰ <https://www.jstor.org/stable/27800346>

³¹ Larry Catá Backer Economic Globalization Ascendant: Four Perspectives on the Emerging Ideology of the State in the New Global Order LA Raza Law Journal , volume 17 , issue 1 , p. 141 - 168 Posted: 2006

An essential goal of civil society is to hold violators of human rights accountable. Grassroots movements and NGOs play an important role in strengthening accountability mechanisms both at home and abroad. It has worked with global institutions, including the International Criminal Court (ICC) and other regional courts of human rights, to deliver justice to those responsible for gross human rights violations.

Civil society often fills the gap at the local level where the administration of justice in a country is either weak or corrupted. Through litigation of abuse cases, exposure of corruption, and pushing for legal reforms, organizations achieve this. Their active involvement in the observation of the actions of governments makes sure that the states are held accountable to their obligations under international human rights law.³²

After all, civil society also plays a very important role outside the courts as it can wage advocacy, public shaming, and international lobbying campaigns that generate the momentum required for institutional reforms and changes in policy.

3. Difficulties of Civil Society

Notwithstanding the crucial contributions civil society makes to human rights protection, civil society organizations are facing crucial challenges throughout the world—in conflict zones and under authoritarian regimes, among others. Critical challenges often arise from shrinking space for civil society operations: governments that increasingly adopt legal and regulatory frameworks that were initially designed to repress dissent are now employing those very restrictions to restrain NGO activities.³³

Harassment, violence, and intimidation are also among the main plights of civil society organizations. In repressive environments, activists and human rights defenders are frequently victimized by the state and non-state actors. Many parts of the world experience physical violence, arbitrary detention, and even assassinations of human rights defenders. And of course, dreadful reminders abound—the murder of Berta Cáceres in Honduras, harassment of activists in Russia and Venezuela. These are stark reminders of the dangers of working on human rights in hostile environments.³⁴

4. The Future of Civil Society in Human Rights Advocacy

Going forward, civil society will need to be plugged into an increasingly complex world in which authoritarianism, populism, and nationalism are the buzzwords. The future of human rights advocacy depends, to a considerable extent, on the innovative abilities of civil society organizations, their building of transnational alliances, effective use of new digital tools, and navigation of associated risks related to technology.³⁵

³² https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=1886470

³³ BIEKART, K.

The Politics of Civil Society Building: European Private Aid Agencies and Democratic Transitions in Central America, International Books/Transnational Institute, Utrecht, 1998.

³⁴ <https://muse.jhu.edu/article/13866>

³⁵ <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/books/mono/10.4324/9780203446102/human-rights-private-wrongs-alison-brysk>

International collaboration and the setting up of global networks will prove essential in the success of civil society as it pushes forward for human rights. Governments are becoming ever more effective at stifling internal civil society activity, and hence transnational networks can be crucial allies-in helping to share resources, information, and strategies. It can only be by having many interlocking links that human rights organisations are able to push through in even the most hostile environments.

Added to this must be the constant pressure from civil society to protect civic space and reverse laws and policies that undermine their work. Such efforts should be supported by international bodies, donors, and others within the system by providing resources, funding, and even platforms for advocacy.

Overall, human rights find an essential bastion in civil society. While society faces many daunting tasks at any given time, organizations in civil society have continued to take the lead in holding different societies accountable to deliver justice and security for citizens' rights. Only through resilience and elasticity will such evolving nations bridge some of the human rights issues of tomorrow.

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